

Readme

Here is a brief description of the two documents contained in this online repository. The first document contains the protocol with the interview questions we applied. The questions were extracted from the checklist available in the work of Agarwal et al. [1]. The second document contains a list of all fairness evaluation technologies and their respective references, which we pre-selected from the dataset provided in the master's research by Silva et al. [2]. We present the material in the table below.

Content

FileName	Description
List_of_Technologies.pdf	List of the technologies that can be applied for fairness evaluation
Script_Interview.pdf	Document with the questions we applied during the interviews

References:

[1] Avinash Agarwal and Harsh Agarwal. 2024. A seven-layer model with checklists for standardising fairness assessment throughout the AI lifecycle. In AI and Ethics. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-023-00266-9>

[2] SILVA, Jhessica Victoria Santos da. Avaliaao de ferramentas de tica em modelos de linguagem desenvolvidos em portugues. 2024. 1 recurso online (117 p.) Dissertaao (mestrado) - Universidade Estadual de Campinas (UNICAMP), Instituto de Computaao, Campinas, SP. Disponivel em: <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12733/24297>. Acesso em: 5 jun. 2025.